

Examining the Reciprocal Effects of Firm-Level Changes and Power Shifts in Global Value Chains

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Introduction.

The phenomenon of Global Value Chains (GVCs) is an integral component of the intricate architecture of today's global economy. GVCs map out the multitude of interconnected activities undertaken by firms and workers, right from the conception of a product to its end use, including but not limited to design, production, marketing, distribution, and after-sales services. Not just a linear, one-way flow, GVCs represent a labyrinthine network of transactions and interactions that cut across national boundaries to co-create value (Gereffi et al, 2005; Jones et al, 2019; Thun, 2020).

The genesis of GVCs lies in the ashes of World War II when the world saw a marked shift from national production systems towards transnational frameworks. The acceleration of trade liberalisation, coupled with breakthroughs in transport, communication, and information processing technologies, fueled the growth of globalised production and trade (Archibugi, 2008; Gilpin & Gilpin, 2001; Trommer, 2020). This transformation from an insular model of production to a fragmented, dispersed paradigm became a compelling economic strategy for firms to survive and thrive in the cut-throat competitive global market (Hay, 2020; Strange, 1994; Trommer, 2020).

The intricacies of GVCs have paved the way for a plethora of conceptual frameworks to analyse their multi-dimensional facets. Notably, the global commodity chains framework focuses on understanding the power dynamics and governance structures within these chains (Gereffi et al, 2005; McGrew, 2020). Similarly, value chain governance theory throws light on how lead firms control the organisation of value chains and dictate the distribution of value (Thun, 2020). The global production networks perspective adds another layer to this understanding by considering the influence of broader economic, social, and institutional contexts on chain operations.

Understanding the importance and relevance of GVCs in the context of the contemporary global economic landscape is crucial. These networks are the lifeblood of the global economy, deeply influencing the distribution of wealth, power, and opportunities (Gilpin & Gilpin, 2001; Hay, 2020; Jessop, 2002; Strange, 1994). They allow firms and nations to specialise in specific stages of production, thereby fostering efficiency and driving economic growth. However, the flip side includes challenges like equitable distribution of value, labour rights, and environmental sustainability (Hay, 2020). In essence, GVCs shape and are shaped by the geopolitical, economic, and social relations among nations, thereby becoming an integral part of the discourse around global development, inequality, and governance (Thun, 2020).

Understanding The Firm And Global Value Chains (GVCs).

Firms, by definition, are organised entities primarily involved in the production and distribution of goods or services with the aim to generate profit. Ranging from small-scale operations to MNCs, these organisations constitute the basic building blocks of an economy and significantly influence the economic landscape (De Backer. & Miroudot, 2013).

In the contemporary globalised context, the role of firms has evolved from being standalone business entities to becoming integral nodes within GVCs. GVCs represent a comprehensive range of activities, extending across geographical borders, involved in bringing a product or service from its initial concept to the end consumer. This process, often referred to as the 'disintegration of production,' (Feenstra, 1998) entails the distribution of tasks and stages across different firms situated in various parts of the world.

Firms serve as crucial linkages within these GVCs, shaping their structure and functioning through strategic decisions and actions (De Backer. & Miroudot, 2013; Gereffi, 2018; Thun, 2020). The positioning of a firm within a GVC depends on a multitude of factors, including its resources, capabilities, strategic choices, and the broader business environment (Porter, 1990; Thun, 2020). Some firms, often referred to as 'lead firms,' exert significant control over the GVCs, managing key high-value stages such as design, branding, and sales, and coordinating the activities of other firms within the chains (Jones et al, 2019; Thun, 2020). These could be large MNCs or even relatively smaller firms that hold a strong competitive advantage in a specific domain (Porter, 1998). Despite having less control, participation in GVCs provides these firms with opportunities to access new markets, develop capabilities, and potentially move up the value chain (Raei et al, 2019).

The power dynamics within GVCs are determined by the relative bargaining power of firms, their control over critical resources, their ability to innovate, and the nature of the product or industry. The lead firms often exert power by setting standards, controlling access to markets, and determining the distribution of value within the chain (Jones et al, 2019; Thun, 2020). These power dynamics significantly impact the behaviour and performance of firms, influencing not only their business practices but also their socio-economic outcomes.

The relationship between firms and GVCs is pivotal for understanding the dynamics of the global economy. This reciprocal relationship, in which firms shape GVCs and are simultaneously shaped by them, illuminates the process of global value creation, capture, and distribution (Gereffi et al, 2005). It provides insights into how firms can leverage GVCs for growth and competitiveness, while also raising critical questions about exploitation, inequality, sustainability, and governance within these global production networks (Gereffi, 2018).

Changes Within The Firm. Catalysts And Impacts.

Technological advancements within a firm can alter the global power dynamics in GVCs (Gereffi et al, 2005; WEF, 2021). For instance, consider Apple Inc., which has effectively harnessed technological innovations to control the design and marketing stages of its GVC, while outsourcing manufacturing predominantly to locations in Asia, like China (Apple, 2023). This strategy capitalises on structural theories of comparative advantage, where countries specialise in certain stages of the value chain based on their unique strengths and resources (Porter, 1998; Thun, 2020). However, this division of labour has provoked discussions about unequal power relations and value distribution in GVCs, highlighting the interplay of economics, politics, and social considerations in shaping globalisation (Hay, 2020).

Strategic upgrading, another crucial aspect of internal changes within firms, also has significant implications for GVCs.

Analysing the governance structures of GVCs also offers critical insights into how firms are positioned. Governance mechanisms vary, from market coordination to network coordination and hierarchical coordination (Gereffi, 2018). This has significant implications for power and profit distribution within the GVC. Multinational corporations (MNCs) often exercise considerable power, determining the standards, specifications, and terms of participation for other actors in the chain (Porter, 1990; Porter, 1998).

The choice of location for different parts of a value chain significantly impacts the firm's role within the GVC. Firms often balance factors such as production costs, infrastructure, regulatory environment, and access to markets when making location decisions. For instance, China's transformation into a global manufacturing hub (Kee & Tang, 2015) has been driven by factors like low labour costs, infrastructure development, and favourable government policies, making it a favoured location for many MNCs' production activities (Gereffi et al, 2022).

However, this also creates challenges for developing countries, which may struggle to attract FDI or optimize benefits for local firms. Also, as noted with China's growing domestic market, it presents new upgrading opportunities for domestic firms. This mirrors the experience of other developing nations, like Vietnam and Bangladesh, which have tapped into global production networks but are grappling with the challenges of upgrading within these chains (Kee & Tang, 2015; Gereffi et al, 2022).

The global political economy plays a profound role in shaping how internal changes within firms influence their position in GVCs. This intricate interplay manifests across various dimensions, including technology, strategy, scale, branding, governance, and location. Understanding this complex landscape is crucial in navigating the multifaceted world of globalisation and GVCs.

Case Studies Of Firms And Their GVC Influence.

As the gears of global commerce continue to turn, businesses, from nascent start-ups to multinational conglomerates, undergo constant evolution. Changes within these firms, whether due to strategic shifts, technological advancements, or adaptations to political or economic landscapes, can profoundly impact the structure and dynamics of GVCs.

1. Apple Inc. (USA, Consumer Electronics & Software Service).

As a dominant entity within the global consumer electronics and software service industry, Apple Inc. provides a compelling illustration of how internal strategic choices can substantially modify a firm's role and clout within GVCs. Apple's strategic emphasis on innovation and ownership of technology has empowered the firm to command the high-value segments of its GVCs, particularly in product design and branding (Apple, 2023).

A notable internal pivot was Apple's reorientation from a computer-centric company to a leader in consumer electronics, underscored by the introduction of game-changing products such as the iPod, iPhone, and iPad. This strategic shift not only propelled Apple's global stature but also precipitated a transformation in its position within the GVC. By ideating and controlling these pioneering products, Apple managed to secure a significant share of the value, even as the manufacturing processes were largely outsourced to partners such as Foxconn (Gereffi, 2018).

2. Foxconn Technology Group (Taiwan, Electronics Manufacturing).

Foxconn started as a low-value, contract manufacturer. Their experience offers an intriguing insight into how a manufacturing firm can alter its GVC position and provide a distinct perspective on GVC dynamics. As a major manufacturer for global brands like Apple, Dell, and Sony, Foxconn demonstrates how strategic shifts and organisational changes within a firm can impact its role in GVCs (Gereffi, 2018).

With its large-scale manufacturing capabilities and efficient production processes, Foxconn has solidified its role as a key player in the electronics GVC. However, amidst rising labour costs in China and global trade tensions, Foxconn has begun restructuring its operations, including automating certain production lines and expanding in other regions such as Southeast Asia and North America (Gereffi, 2022). This strategy aims to diversify geographical risks and reduce labour costs, indicating how economic and political pressures can shape a firm's strategic choices and consequently, its position in GVCs.

3. Huawei Technologies Co. (China, Consumer Electronics and Telecom Equipment).

Huawei, a global telecommunications and consumer electronics company, demonstrates how a firm can ascend the GVC through strategic upgrading and capability building. Initially a manufacturer of low-cost phone switches, Huawei shifted its strategy to focus on R&D, ultimately becoming a global leader in 5G technology (Lening, 2022).

The company's emphasis on human capital and innovation allowed it to control a more valuable stage in the telecommunications GVC. However, the firm also highlights the interplay of politics and economics in GVCs. Despite its technological leadership, Huawei has faced significant challenges due to geopolitical tensions and concerns about network security.

4. Tesla Inc. (USA, Automotive).

Tesla, the iconic electric vehicle (EV) manufacturer, offers a compelling study of how internal changes within a firm can significantly influence its position within GVCs. Spearheading the shift towards renewable energy, Tesla has harnessed technological advancements to redefine the automotive industry's GVC (Tesla 2022). By integrating processes from battery production to car sales, Tesla has brought significant parts of the value chain in-house, positioning itself as a leader and driving industry standards.

This reshaping of the GVC has been catalysed by Tesla's aggressive R&D strategy, leading to breakthroughs like longer-lasting batteries, improved energy efficiency, and advanced autonomous driving capabilities. This focus on innovation gives Tesla a unique competitive advantage, which it amplifies by protecting its intellectual property rights, a crucial legal consideration in global business (Tesla, 2022).

5. Unilever (UK/Netherlands, Consumer Goods Sector).

Unilever's vast global footprint, with its multitude of products spanning food, beverages, hygiene, and personal care, positions the corporation as a formidable participant in various GVCs. In 2010, a consequential internal shift within the company took shape with the initiation of the Unilever Sustainable Living Plan (Unilever, 2023). The program set a substantial goal: to ensure 100% of agricultural raw materials were sourced sustainably by the end of 2020.

This strategic manoeuvre by Unilever resulted in a profound reorientation of the firm's GVCs. The commitment not only impacted its direct procurement processes but also cascaded downstream, compelling suppliers to adopt sustainable practices. Furthermore, this shift led to the formation of new alliances and partnerships, signalling how internal changes within a firm can extend beyond organisational boundaries.

These case studies illustrate how changes within firms can significantly alter their position and influence in GVCs. Factors such as technological advancements, strategic shifts, investments in capabilities, and even geopolitical considerations come into play, underscoring the complex dynamics that shape global value chains (Gereffi, 2018; Porter, 1998). While these changes can create opportunities for firms to capture greater value and wield more influence, they also present risks and challenges, underscoring the importance of strategic agility and resilience in the globalised economy (Jones et al, 2019; Thun, 2020).

Shifting GVC Power Dynamics. The Reciprocal Impact.

The interconnectedness of GVCs and individual firms is shaped significantly by various external and internal factors, such as shifts in competition, evolving consumer demands, regulatory alterations, and broad economic trends (Porter, 1990). These dynamics exert profound influences on global supply chain management, trade-in value-added, offshoring and outsourcing decisions, competitiveness, and overall economic development and upgrading within firms.

1. Market Dynamics And Resource Allocation.

It is evident that shifts in competition can significantly impact the balance of power within GVCs (Porter, 1990). This can prompt firms to review their offshoring and outsourcing strategies or innovate to maintain or enhance their competitive edge. For instance, the rise of electric vehicles (EVs) in the automotive industry is a clear illustration of a competition-driven shift. If a dominant buyer changes its sourcing strategies due to such shifts, affected firms may need to explore new markets or invest in new capabilities to retain their relevance in the GVC (Tesla, 2022). In this competitive landscape, firms often outsource or offshore parts of their operations to maintain or enhance their competitiveness, redefining their roles in the global value chain (Porter, 1998). Such strategic offshoring and outsourcing decisions can be prompted by shifts in power dynamics within GVCs, which often reflect changes in trade in value-added terms, labour effects, and income distribution (Gereffi et al, 2005; Gereffi, 2018).

2. Regulatory Adjustments And Standards.

Regulatory shifts and industry standards, deeply interwoven with power dynamics within a GVC, can reshape the regulatory landscape. Influential actors may establish stringent quality or sustainability standards, compelling other firms to comply, thereby necessitating considerable internal changes. Shifts in trade policies, such as the imposition of trade barriers, measures, and elevated trade costs, can compel firms to adjust their global supply chain management strategies (Hay, 2020; Feenstra, 1998).

3. Risk Distribution.

Economic development, a significant element of Porter's Competitive Advantage of Nations, can incite shifts in GVC dynamics, influencing firms across different countries (Porter, 1998). These shifts often impact the risk distribution within GVCs. Firms with lesser power may bear more risks, such as demand or price fluctuations, necessitating changes in their risk management strategies for diversifying their customer base and supply sources (Jones et al, 2019).

Global supply chain management becomes a pivotal aspect for firms as they aim to maximise trade in value added. This may involve upgrading their participation in GVCs by moving to higher value-added activities, such as product design or after-sales services. Such an upgrading process can result from external changes in GVCs, such as the rise of new competitors or technologies, prompting internal changes within firms (Gereffi, 2018).

4. Innovation And Efficiency.

Changes in power dynamics can instigate alterations in the competitive landscape, motivating firms to innovate and enhance their operational efficiency. The entry of a powerful new competitor into the GVC might compel existing firms to invest in R&D or enhance their operational efficiency.

Porter's cluster theory further enhances our understanding of these dynamics. Industries tend to cluster geographically, leading to localised networks of suppliers, service providers, and related institutions (Porter, 1990; Porter, 1998). These clusters can become centres of expertise, innovation, and competitive advantage. Shifts in GVC power dynamics can affect the composition and competitiveness of these clusters, leading to changes within firms located within these clusters.

5. Labour And Income.

A firm's competitiveness is also shaped by economic development within its home and host countries. Porter's Competitive Advantage of Nations provides a useful framework for understanding this relationship (Porter, 1998). In an increasingly interconnected world economy, economic development in one nation can shift GVC dynamics, affecting firms across different countries (Thun, 2020). For example, economic development in emerging economies has led to an increase in wage levels and labour costs, which can prompt firms to adjust their sourcing strategies or invest in labour-saving technologies (De Backer & Miroudot, 2013; Jones et al, 2019).

GVC shifts can have significant implications for labour effects and income distribution, both within and across countries. For example, the offshoring of production processes to low-wage countries can lead to job losses in high-wage countries, while potentially improving income distribution in low-wage countries (Gereffi, 2018; Thun, 2020). However, this can also result in downward pressure on wages and working conditions in these countries, especially if they lack strong labour regulations (Raei, 2019). As power dynamics within GVCs shift, firms need to navigate these complex labour and income distribution effects, which can influence their global reputation, labour strategies, and even their social license to operate (Gereffi et al, 2005; Jones et al, 2019).

Case Studies On GVC Shifts And Their Firm-Level Effects.

In elucidating the dynamic relationship between GVCs and firms, it is instructive to consider real-world examples that demonstrate how shifts in GVCs enforce changes within firms. We explore a few key examples that provide a diverse representation of experiences and outcomes, focusing on the areas of global supply chain management, trade-in value-added, offshoring, outsourcing, competitiveness, economic development, upgrading, trade barriers and measures, trade cost, labour effect, and income distribution.

1. Samsung (South Korea, Electronics and Information Technology).

The South Korean conglomerate Samsung Electronics serves as a pertinent example of how changes in GVCs can enforce alterations within a firm (Gereffi, 2018). In the early 2000s, when the electronics industry experienced a significant surge in the demand for memory chips, Samsung capitalised on its strong footing in semiconductor manufacturing. This GVC shift saw Samsung focusing more on its semiconductor business, leading to significant internal realignments. The firm not only scaled up its production but also invested heavily in research and development to maintain its competitive edge (Samsung, 2023). However, as the GVC further evolved, the increasing commoditisation and price competition in the memory chip industry prompted Samsung to diversify its offerings, ultimately leading to its dominance in the smartphone market.

2. BHP Billiton (Australia, Mining and Resources).

BHP Billiton, a leading global resources company, had to adjust its operations and strategies in response to shifting GVC dynamics in the commodities market. Rising demand from developing economies, notably China, and fluctuations in commodity prices significantly impacted the firm's position in the resources GVC (BHP, 2022; Thun, 2020). To manage this, BHP Billiton diversified its portfolio, invested in technology to improve operational efficiency,

and adopted more flexible market strategies. The firm's adjustments underline how changes in consumer demand and global economic trends can drive firms to make internal changes.

3. Vestas Wind Systems (Denmark, Renewable Energy Industry).

The rise of the renewable energy sector has shifted the GVC towards cleaner, sustainable technologies. Vestas, as a leading wind turbine manufacturer, has had to continuously adapt to this evolving GVC (Vestas, 2021). Technological advancements, changing regulations, and increased competition have led Vestas to focus on continuous innovation, cost reduction, and global supply chain management to stay competitive.

These case studies serve as tangible demonstrations of how shifts in GVC dynamics can result in significant firm-level effects. They underline the necessity for firms to remain agile and responsive to the evolving global supply chain landscape, reinforcing the pivotal role of strategic global supply chain management (Jones et al, 2019; Raeli, 2019). Firms can respond by upgrading their operations and products to a complete strategic overhaul, indicating the profound impact of GVC shifts. The diverse experiences and outcomes also highlight that there is no one-size-fits-all solution, with each firm needing to navigate its unique path through the complexities of GVC dynamics. The strategies and trajectories adopted by these firms, in response to the GVC shifts, carry valuable lessons for other enterprises navigating similar challenges (Jones et al, 2019; Gereffi, 2018).

Conclusion And Future Prospects.

Looking towards the future, several trends promise to further shape the relationship between firms and GVCs. The rise of digitalisation and automation technologies is already reshaping industries (WEF, 2019), and these trends will continue to influence GVC power dynamics, requiring firms to continuously upgrade their capabilities (Jones et al, 2019). The ongoing transition towards a greener, more sustainable economy will likely have substantial implications for GVCs and the firms operating within them. These trends indicate that the reciprocal dynamics between firms and GVCs will continue to evolve, underscoring the importance of ongoing research in this field.

From a policy perspective, this analysis suggests that policymakers need to consider these dynamics when developing trade, industrial, and innovation policies. Policies that support firms in upgrading their capabilities, navigating regulatory changes, and transitioning towards more sustainable practices can enhance the competitiveness of firms within GVCs (Porter, 1990; Porter, 1998). At the same time, policymakers need to consider the potential implications of these changes on labour effects and income distribution, ensuring that the benefits of GVC participation are widely shared (Hay, 2020; Thun 2020).

Understanding the reciprocal dynamics between firms and GVCs is vital for both firms navigating the global business landscape and policymakers aiming to enhance economic development (Gereffi, 2018). As GVCs continue to evolve, firms will need to be agile and adaptive, ensuring that they are equipped to leverage opportunities and navigate challenges in this complex, globalised economy.

References

- Apple. (2023). *How We Work with Suppliers*. Available from: <https://www.apple.com/supplier-responsibility/pdf/How-We-Work-With-Suppliers.pdf> (Accessed 03 July 2023)
- Archibugi, D. (2008). *The Global Commonwealth of Citizens: Toward Cosmopolitan Democracy*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- BHP (2022). *Value Chain Sustainability*. Available from: <https://www.bhp.com/sustainability/value-chain-sustainability> (Accessed 03 July 2023).
- De Backer, K. & Miroudot, S. (2013). Mapping Global Value Chains. *OECD Trade Policy Papers, No. 159*, OECD Publishing, Paris. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5k3v1trgnbr4-en>
- Feenstra, R. (1998). Integration of Trade and Disintegration of Production in the Global Economy. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 12(4): 31-50. DOI: 10.1257/jep.12.4.31
- Gereffi, G., Humphrey, J. & Sturgeon, T. (2005). The Governance of Global Value Chains. *Review of International Political Economy*, 12(1): 78-104.
- Gereffi, G. (2018). *Global Value Chains and Development: Redefining the Contours of 21st Century Capitalism*. UK: Cambridge University Press
- Gilpin, R. & Gilpin, J. (2001). *Global Political Economy: Understanding The International Economic Order*. NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Hay, C. (2020). Globalization's Impact On States, Chapter 11 in Ravenhill, J. *Global Political Economy (6th ed)*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Jessop, B. (2002). *The Future of the Capitalist State*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Jones, L., Demirkaya, M., & Bethmann, E. (2019). Global Value Chain Analysis: Concepts and Approaches. *Journal of International Commerce and Economics*, April 2019.
- Kee, H. L. & Tang, H. (2015). *Domestic value added in exports: theory and firm evidence from China*. Policy Research no. WPS 7491. World Bank Group. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/125771468185954603/Domestic-value-added-in-exports-theory-and-firm-evidence-from-China>
- Lening, X. (2022). *How Huawei Transformed Its Supply Chain In the Digital Era*. HuaweiTech 2022, 03. Available from: <https://www.huawei.com/en/huaweitech/publication/202203/huawei-reshape-supply-chain-digital-era> (Accessed 03 July 2023)
- McGrew, A. (2020). The Logics Of Economic Globalization, Chapter 10 in Ravenhill, J. *Global Political Economy (6th ed)*. Oxford: Oxford University Press

- Porter, M. (1990). *The Competitive Advantage of Nations*. Available from:
<https://hbswk.hbs.edu/item/porters-perspective-competing-in-the-global-economy> (Accessed 02 July 2023)
- Porter, M. (1998). Clusters and the New Economics of Competition. *Harvard Business Review*, 76(6) (November–December 1998): 77–90.
- Raei, F., Ignatenko, A., & Mircheva, B. (2019). Global Value Chains: What are the Benefits and Why Do Countries Participate? *IMF Working Papers*. 19(1). 10.5089/9781484392928.001.
- Samsung (2023). *Sustainable Supply Chain*. Available from:
<https://www.samsung.com/us/sustainability/sustainable-supply-chain/> (Accessed 04 July 2023).
- Strange, S. (1994). *States & Markets (2nd ed)*. New York: Continuum
- Tesla. (2022). *Impact Report 2022*. Available from: https://www.tesla.com/en_gb/impact/supply-chain (Accessed 03 July 2023)
- Thun, E. (2020). The Globalization of Production, Chapter 07 in Ravenhill, J. *Global Political Economy (6th ed)*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Trommer, S. (2020). The Evolution of the Global Trade Regime, Chapter 5 in Ravenhill, J., *Global Political Economy (6th ed)*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Unilever (2023). *Unilever Sustainable Living Plan 2010 to 2020*. Available at:
<https://www.unilever.com/files/92ui5egz/production/16cb778e4d31b81509dc5937001559f1f5c863ab.pdf> (Accessed 03 July 2023)
- Vestas (2021). *Sustainability Report 2021*. Available from:
<https://www.vestas.de/content/dam/vestas-com/global/en/sustainability/reports-and-ratings/sustainability-reports/Sustainability%20Report%202021.pdf> (Accessed 02 July 2023)
- WEF (2019). *Globalization 4.0: Shaping a New Global Architecture in the Age of the Fourth Industrial Revolution*. Available at: https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Globalization_4.0_Call_for_Engagement.pdf (Accessed 04 July 2023).